

Safety Services in Hospital

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Abstract:- In the modern era, safety services in the hospitals are of great importance. Patients come to the hospitals for consultation because they are physically and mentally weak and they are not in a condition to be able to do their day to day activities. It is the responsibility of the hospitals to take care of the safety of the patients as well as the staff which works in the hospital. It is important to regularly maintain the safety equipment's in the hospitals for example maintaining fire extinguishers and lifts regularly. It is important to give proper training and guidance to the staff related to safety issues so that they can follow the instructions when needed specially in situations like handling new born babies in the hospitals, which require special skills and care.

Keywords:- Safety Services in Hospitals, Security of Patients and Staff, Innovation, Efficiency.

I. INTRODUCTION

Hospital is a place where patients come in a hope that their problems will be solved and people come there to get medical advice and hope that they will get well. When People come to a hospital they expect to get medical advice about the problems related to their body, being hopeful that the hospital will provide good health facilities. Safety of the patients is one of the most important issues that is needed to be attended in a hospital, because there are many issues like transmission of infection from one person to another which must be managed hygienically. Corona Virus has further taught us how important it is to provide the clean environment to the patients as well as the doctors and working staff in a hospital, giving special attention for the wellbeing along with the health benefits of their patients.

There are different types of safety devices or work equipment's in a hospital. Work equipment can be any machine, appliance or an apparatus used with in a hospital, For example testing facility in a lab of a hospital. One must take precautionary measures while conducting lab tests in a hospital, which requires clean apparatus for accurate results. For this reason the scope of the safety facilities in a hospital is wide which is found in every department. It is not only these technical safety features that must be taken care in a hospital but also some basic needs such as availability of wheel chairs and proper functioning of lifts etc.

II. WHAT IS SAFETY?

In simple words safety means to avoid any type of risk or danger or to protect from any loss. Safety is something which is needed everywhere for example on roads, in industry, construction work and even in hospitals. Safety is used in all kinds of work, whether it is use of helmets and safety jackets in construction work use of gloves in hospitals, guidance of a supervisor while working in Tunnels. Everywhere the safety rules are followed and must not be neglected.

III. SAFETY SERVICES IN HOSPITAL

There are safety codes in a hospital. The information of these safety codes is given to the staff from time to time. There is huge importance of safety codes in a hospital to avoid any kind of miss happening or accident. Some common safety codes followed are as follows:

CODE RED	Fire
CODE PINK	Emergency infant/child
CODE BLUE	Cardiac arrest
CODE BLACK	Bomb threat/ suspicious object
CODE ORANGE	External disaster
CODE YELLOW	Internal disaster
CODE VIOLET	Violent patient / violent attender... Cote activate

As a healthcare provider, it is not only important but mandatory that best services are provided to the patients. Imagine a situation when someone did not choose a hospital but have to be operated there, in that case you would be very much scared and anxious about the situation. One would feel horrible if he/she comes to know that hospital where they are admitted holds a poor reputation. The patient or the care takers in that case would be afraid. This is the reason why the safety codes must be controlled efficiently in every health care provider.

These safety codes are activated in an Emergency situation in a hospital. The hospitals also have contract with the governmental agencies in case of emergency, For example the fire Extinguisher department. The hospitals are constructed in such a way that fire extinguisher department can get the access to each and every side of the hospital for safety of patients.

The safety of the employees and the doctors is of more importance in a hospital because the staff working in the X-Ray Labs and Radiology department is vulnerable to waves which are harmful. Therefore the availability of safety jackets such Thyroid shield, Pelvic shield and other safety equipment is important and also to follow the rules while crossing such places.

Safety begins with sanitizing your hands. Not only hands but safety is considered while taking the patient to the ward or taking the patient from one place to the other.

IV. NECESSITY OF SAFETY SERVICES

In a hospital patients come on a daily basis, not only patients but the people who know them also come on a regular basis. The details of every such person are taken by the security team. There are two types of patients who come to the hospital, Patients who need emergency care and other one is people who need to go to OPD ward. Now people who have emergency conditions need very accurate services so that their lives can be saved. Presence of medical oxygen is one of such needs which also come under safety features. Such patients must be given facilities in such a manner that any further damage possible to such patients can be avoided and they do not feel any mental or physical stress while being treated in the hospital or while being shifted.

That is why there is also a maintenance department in the hospital, those who look after the hospital building, power supply, and firefighting equipment and does their maintenance from time to time, take care of the safety of the patient as well as the hospital administration and the hospital staff. Some type of safety jobs that are needed to be done in a hospital are as follows:

(A) In Case of Fire

In a hospital the need of fire extinguishing equipment is required in case of sudden fire, when the rescue team takes out the patients safely then the firefighting team plays an important role in controlling the fire. If the firefighting team of the hospital fails to control the fire, then the government's fire brigade is called, whose personnel have already been trained to extinguish the fire.

(B) In Case of Cardiac Arrest

When a person suffers from heart attack, the hospital staff activates code blue and the team reaches there and leads the patient to the emergency room giving CPR.

(C) In Case of Child Abduction

If for any reason the baby is stolen or missing from the hospital after delivery then code pink is activated. Its training is also given to the hospital staff in advance. The main entrance and exit gate are closed.

(D) Needle Stick Injury

A Needle Stick Injury is a percutaneous piercing wound typically. Whenever in the ward working staff gets needle injury its report is recorded as Needle stick injury according to NABH. The blood sample of the concerned person is

collected and sent for testing. To avoid injury, it is necessary to burn or destroy syringe needle after use. And there were many situations where caution is needed in such cases.

V. WHATARE SAFETY EQUIPMENT AND THEIR MAINTENANCE

Safety devices are those devices which are used in case of accidental events. The range of fire extinguishing safety equipment in the hospital is as follows:

- Fire Extinguisher (Co2, Dry Powder Etc.).
- Smoke Detector.
- Fire Hydrant.
- Fire Blanket.
- Fire House.
- Fire Alarm

SAFETY EQUIPMENT FOR PATIENTS

WHEELCHAIR

RESTRAINERS

LIFT

HANDLE IN DESIRED

PLACES LIKE

RAMP, LIFT, AND TOILET.

STRETCHER

These items are used for patient safety. Such safety equipment's used for handicap patients to take them from one place to another. Without this equipment it could be harmful to move patients from one place to another, such as moving a patient from Emergency ward to the General Ward.

Some equipment's are also necessary for the staff in their day to day activities.

VI. FOR RADIOLOGY STAFF

LEAD APRON: it is used for safety from x-ray radiation.

THYROID SHIELD: it is used to protect thyroid gland from radiation while working in x-rays rooms.

PELVIC SHIELD: it used for safety of internal body parts due to radiation.

Equipment for other staff member:

APRON: it is used by lab technicians who work in the lab.

GLOVES: it is used for protection of direct infection.

MASK: To protect staff from infection and patients when they are close to other patients who can transmit Diseases which can spread in air.

➤ Telephone:

Telephone is also a mandatory requirement in the hospitals for communication and to activate the safety code with the help of the phone. Phone can help the hospital staff to inform the security room about any accident or any emergency situation and to activate the safety code by transferring information from one department to another by means of communication.

There is fire exit plan on each floor of the hospital and the fire exit route is mentioned and these routes are used in case of emergency situation and are helpful for execution.

➤ *Maintenance of Equipment's:*

Maintenance of fire safety equipment's:

Regular routine maintenance of such equipment's is necessary. It is important to inspect all such equipment's and to refill them and their replacement when needed and also procedures like Hydro pressure test to make Sure that these equipment's will work properly when needed.

➤ **Inspection** in this some important things to check in :

- Fire extinguisher is properly placed in the right place and Safety pin and temper seal is properly placed or not.
- Cylinders of fire extinguishers are full.
- Pressure Gauge is in range or not.

According to ISO:2190 guidelines the life of Fire extinguishers is only 10 years and these norms must be followed strictly for the safety of every person.

➤ *Lift Elevator*

Maintenance of lift elevator is also important from time to time. It can be life threatening if an Elevator stops or any other problem occurs in the functioning of elevator. It is one the most important facility used in the hospitals these days. It is used by the patients in moving from one floor to other and also by the staff to efficiently move from place to other to save time and to travel faster in case of emergency.

VII. CONCLUSION

Safety services in the hospitals are used to keep everyone safe, including staff, patients and visitors. Hospitals use different types of security measures which include CCTV cameras, Alarms, Electronic security for doors and OPD and emergency ward. Another way of keeping everyone safe in the hospitals is by making sure that the patients do not pick up infections or take wrong medication or feel pressure while being treated in the hospital. Such measures can be achieved by putting strict measures as well, such as not allowing outside food, flowers etc. Safety is one of the most important aspect is today's world, especially after the erosion of covid-19 pandemic recently; we have seen how viruses and infections can transmit. Therefore in modern world today where everything is fast, we must follow the rules being set for our safety. In a country like India, where there are concerns about the hygiene and cleanliness in some places, we must be more concerned about the safety services.

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